

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

VOLUME 4, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2024

PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA

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**FOSTERING REGIONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT THROUGH A
DECENTRALISED PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM KUMBA AND TIKO
MUNICIPALITIES, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON**

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Submission Date: 05/04/2024

Acceptation Date: 15/06/2024

Abstract

This study sets out to assess the role of councils in achieving sustainable development in Kumba and Tiko municipalities. In order to achieve the goal of this study, a survey research design was adopted. The sample size of the study comprised of 100 respondents made up of 30 council workers and 70 inhabitants and the sampling technique used was the stratified, purposive and snowballing sampling techniques. Data were equally collected using a semi-structured interview technique. Data collected were analysed qualitatively and statistical data were presented on tables using a quantitative data analysis technique. Results reveal that both Councils have to an extent been able to contribute to the achievement of some of the SDGs. Lagging in the achievement of Goals 5, 8, 9 to 17. Findings also reveal that the Councils lack financial resources, skilled personnel, adequate training by the technical department and face challenges in creating new partnership with investors. The study therefore concludes that local councils have inclusive development visions and initiatives which are promising development initiatives to improve the wellbeing of their local communities if well planned and executed. The study recommends that there is a need to mobilise the community through civic participation namely enhanced participatory budgeting that could engage citizens and facilitate revenue collection.

Key Words: Regional growth, Regional Development, Sustainable development, Decentralisation, Kumba, Tiko, South West Region

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1 Introduction

The world's urban population has witnessed a constant increase since the Industrial Revolution. According to the 2016 Stockholm Security Conference on Secure Cities, only 10% of the World's population lived in cities during the 1900s. Today, the figure stands at over 50% and expected to reach around 75% by 2050. This urbanisation rate is highest in developing countries, especially those located south of the Sahara and cities of the Asian continent (UNSTATS, 2022). Africa within the 1900s show an estimated 95% of its inhabitants living on primary occupations like farming, hunting and gathering, cattle nomadism and fishing (Aase, 2003). In 1950, however, 14.7% of Africa's population especially countries South of the Sahara became urban. This figure rose to 37.2% in 2000 and it went to over 45.3% in 2015 given an annual urbanisation rate of 3.35% (UN, 2002). Currently, Africa's urban population stands at 609 million with an estimated rise to 722 million of the urban population by 2026 (UNHABITAT, 2023). Lagos for example had a population of over 665000 inhabitants by 1963 (Rakodi, 1997) and 8.7 million by 2000. In 2023, the city had a population of over 16.5 million inhabitants with a growth rate of 3.54% (UN, 2023). This high rate of urbanisation is largely due to centralised growth within the cities for expected transmission of development impulses to surrounding settlements (Agbortoko, 2016). As a result, most regions in Africa have grown with single cities that dominate all other surrounding settlements - a term described as primate cities (Fombe, 2006). Primate cities today, constitute centres of growth, learning, health, industries among others while the rural counterpart depends to a large extent for all these facilities from the urban centre (Fogwe, 2005).

The concept of regional development is a broad term used to describe the general efforts of policies that enhance well-being and living standards of a region, from cities to rural areas, and the improvement of their contribution to national performance for a more inclusive and resilient society (OECD, 2020). These policies vary from country to country but most often, regions are divided politically or based on their natural resources present. Whichever the case, the most important is the development of these regions to improve the lives of their inhabitants. Regional development policies or place-based policies, generally aimed at reducing regional disparities, by supporting economic growth within and between regions. This makes regions to be competitive, inclusive, and resilient with stakeholder involvement (Capello, 2017).

Regional growth and development in most African countries are to a larger extent characterised by unbalanced growth and development with wide dispersion in employment and income outcomes (OECD, 2019). Such wide gaps in development within the same region constitute the basic reasons for rural-urban migration as the rural population move to cities to seek out better lifestyles in the urban milieu (UNHABITAT, 2006). The Rio 91 concept of Local Agenda 21 and SDG Goal 11 to create sustainable and inclusive cities brings forth a need to rethink on the pattern of regional growth and development in Africa. The Local Agenda 21 concept emphasises on the need for central governments to empower local governments if balanced development must be achieved in both rural and urban environments. This policy is today termed the decentralisation policy, whereby most governments have devolved powers to local councils for the development of the entire region/country. According to Capello et al. (2011), the decentralisation policy in a regional perspective seeks to understand socio-economic

processes and inequalities at regional levels that position regions at core places of policy actions. However, this has not been the case in Cameroon as since the adoption of the Decentralisation Law in 1994, very little has been achieved in this direction. This paper therefore seeks to examine the regional growth and development trends of the South West Region of Cameroon using case studies of one City Council area, the Kumba City Council and one Sub-divisional Council area, the Tiko Sub-divisional Council to draw lessons for improvement in some social and economic aspects that can enhance balanced and inclusive development.

2 Literature Review

The major concepts are the Trickle-down and the polarization effects by Hirschman (1989)

2.1 Trickle-down effect

Growth is unbalanced in geographical space because of the occurrence of earth's resources. It is through the development of favoured areas that the unfavoured tends to benefit. It is the benefits from the favoured to unfavoured that Hirschman refers to as "trickle down" which can take the form of trade interaction between the growth point (urban) and surrounding rural areas. Rural traders selling to urbanites generate some income for investment and further production. Similarly, urban industries absorb the disguise unemployment of the periphery. This raises the latter's marginal productivity of labour. According to Hirschman (1989), such process eventually leads to growth and development in both core and periphery areas.

2.2 Polarisation effect

Polarisation is the process by which there is the development of poles of growth, surrounded by smaller growth points like villages. They are all mutually interdependent in the development process which begins from the favoured pole and spreads out to the unfavoured poles. The pole acts as a converging and disseminating point in terms of production and distribution of good/services and the spatial development process through regional integration. Despite the disparities between the favoured and unfavoured poles, Hirschman believed that some benefits from the favoured pole will eventually reach the periphery thereby accelerating balanced growth and development in a long run.

Based on the concept, it is realised that growth poles are supposed to spread out impulses of development to their surrounding satellites in order to generate equal growth opportunities to the entire region. The concept insists on trickle down and polarization of development impulses through policy integration of activities and spread of development indicators throughout the entire region in order to bridge the gap between the rural and urban settlements. However, the sectoral delineation of policies bridging the urban and rural areas has restricted growth inducement from urban to rural areas thereby widening the development gap between rural and urban areas. This study therefore examines the concept of trickle down and polarisation effect through a decentralised perspective in order to draw policy conclusions.

2.3 Role of Councils in Sustainable Development

Based on the first two concepts of Trickle-down and polarisation effects, it can be concluded that the role of the councils is to ease development of the local population and

reduce the distance between power control and the population. Therefore, when councils have decentralised powers, they bring the power and decision-making close to the population as illustrated in Figure 1.

Based on Fig. 1, it is realised that once councils are able to mobilise their resources, they will be able to carry out developmental projects that can help improve high living standards, poverty alleviation, infrastructural development, job creation and an overall attainment of the SDGs by 2030. The framework acknowledges the possibility of some eminent challenges like limited support, long period of wait for loans to be awarded by FEICOM and PNDP, challenges faced during mobilisation of resources through revenue collection among others.

Looking at the sustainable development agenda, it can be deduced that, the devolution of some powers from the central government to regional and local governments stands as a way forward to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. This can be achieved through the realisation of projects that would ameliorate the living standards of the population as seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Role of Councils in achieving Sustainable Development

Source: Author (2023)

3 The Study Area and Methodology

3.1 Study Area

The South West Region constitutes one of the ten regions of Cameroon. It is located between 5°12'0.00" N and 9°18'0.00" E as illustrated in Map 1. The region is made up of six Divisions: Fako (hosting Tiko sub-division), Kupe Manengouba, Manyu, Meme (hosting Kumba I, II and III Sub-divisions), Lebialem, and Ndian Divisions. The administrative capital of South West Region is Fako Division and Meme Division being the economic capital. It is therefore expected that these two Divisions constitute the most developed of all the other seven. Historically, the South West Region was colonised by Germany under the Protectorate regime in 1884. By 1916, it became a condominium, jointly administered by France and the United Kingdom. In 1919, the Region was solely administered by the British and in 1961; the Region joined the rest of Cameroon to become one unified country.

The South West Region according to projections from 2015 stands at over 1,553,320 inhabitants with a growth rate of 1.67% (NIS, 2019). The South West Region has a surface area of over 25,410km² and a population density of 61/km². Besides being the capital of the Southwest Region, Buea, is the administrative capital of Fako Division and hosts the lone University of the Region and the Mount Cameroon which stands as the highest peak in West and Central Africa.

Map 1: Location of Tiko in Fako Division of the South West Region, Cameroon

Source: Adapted from the Forba (2008)

The rainfall pattern in the South West Region is largely modified by Mount Cameroon with its highland that interrupts the movement of air masses causing considerable orographic rainfall. Buea especially and other towns located along the mountain flanks like Limbe and Tiko record an annual rainfall of over 3500mm (IRAD, Ekona, 1993). Temperatures are considerably high with low annual variations. The mean annual temperature is 26°C while the monthly temperature reveals a minimum of about 20°C in the month of June and July accounted for by heavy rainfall in these months.

3.2 Research Methodology

In order to arrive at the stated objectives, the study adopted a survey approach in data collection. Secondary source data were obtained from the Regional Archive in Buea as well as from published thesis, articles and newspapers. The collection of primary data was through the use of a systematic sampling technique. The target population constituted the local council authorities, local chiefs, Delegate of Urban Development and Housing, some workers in the Regional Council concerned with economic and social development.

The different authorities were grouped in the same stratum and the population in another. Focus group discussions were conducted with the population of some rural communities like Ikiliwindi, Bombe, Barombi Mbo, Mbonge, Kake I, Mabanda and Mokonje, Mile 4 quarters, Busumbu, Bomaka, Muea, Bokwango, Bulu, Tiko wharf quarters and Yoke. It should be noted that these communities are largely agricultural. Therefore this study took into consideration ease of movement of agricultural produce, health facilities available, educational amenities, electricity and pipe borne water supply. For the urban sector, a number of government and local agencies as mentioned above were consulted to understand the role they play in regional development and provision of amenities to both rural and urban environments. Field survey was also done to confirm information from focus group discussions and direct interviews.

Data collected were analysed using descriptive analysis. The approach involves the use of percentages represented in the form of charts, tables, plates and other diagrams. Field results were presented and analysed descriptively following the areas under investigation like transportation, health, education, drinking water provision among others as evident in the field.

4. Results

The South West Region holds a significant potential for regional growth and development. With its rich cultural heritage, fertile lands, and strategic location, this region has the capacity to thrive and contribute to the overall progress of the country. However, in order to fully harness its potential, a decentralised perspective is essential.

4.1 State of Regional Development in Cameroon

Regional Councils were created following the adoption of the revised 1996 constitution after calls for return to a federated system of governance/improved decentralisation. As enshrined in the constitution, councils will have control over cultural, economic, educational, health, social and sports related issues within their area of jurisdiction. However, these Regional Councils only became a reality on December 6, 2020 when the Regional Councillors were voted and installed in their offices, December 22, 2020.

The evidence of Decentralisation in Cameroon dates as far back as 1922 with the British Cameroons (Cheka, 2007). However, large scale sweeping reforms took place in the 1980 and 1990s. The on-going process of decentralisation draws its powers from *Law No. 96/06 of 18 January 1996*, especially in its Article 55 which states that the decentralized local entities of the Republic shall be the Regions and the Councils. The law recognizes the councils as legal entities that underpin administrative and financial autonomy and for the interest of the local people by their elected representatives (Fru, 2016). The trio law of decentralisation in Cameroon pursuant to *Law No. 2004/17 of 22 July, 2004* on the Orientation of Decentralisation, *Law No. 2004/18 of July, 2004* comprising rules

applicable to Councils, and Law No. 2004/19 of 22 July, 2004 comprising rules applicable to Regions; this marked a turning point in the roles because the laws gave autonomous powers to councils henceforth (Emeka, 2007).

According to Part III of Law No. 2004/19 of 22 July 2004 to lay down rules applicable to Regions, Regional Councils are charged with economic development (management of the environment and natural resources, planning, regional development, public works, town planning and housing); Health and social development (Health and social action); Educational, sports and cultural development (education, literacy, and vocational training, youth, sports and leisure, culture and development of national languages) as areas of powers devolved upon Regional Councils. In order for these objectives to be arrived at, Regional Councils must work closely with local councils for the development of local communities and regions as a whole. To this end, some of the salient contributions made by councils towards the development of their communities can be viewed under education, health, infrastructure and economic development.

4.2 Strengths of Decentralisation

The decentralisation process has as fundamental objective to promote development at the local level as spelt out in Law N° 018/2004 of 22nd July 2004 on the orientation of decentralisation. The process empowers the Councils and gives them access to evaluate the problems faced by the local population and ameliorate the living standards of the people more efficiently and faster than being managed from the top, bringing the centre of decision making closer to the people. To achieve this, the State devolved both power and resources to enable the council carry out local development. As follow up of the devolution of powers, a time table was put in place for the devolution process to begin from 2010 and by 2015 all ministries were expected to transfer the necessary power and resources to the councils. Since 2010, just sixteen ministries have handed down resources to councils for management as reflected in projects realised. This in a way has alleviated poverty as contracts are now awarded to locals and not to favourites from the top. Also, these contracts are closely supervised by the beneficiary community through the City Mayor and or the Lord Mayor of the municipality, which makes it to be better evaluated and monitored. In this process of development, the state has assigned partners that accompany the councils to achieve their development goals. These partners are the P.N.D.P and FEICOM. These bodies are involved in the development aspect of decentralisation by funding projects identified by the councils.

Based on results obtained from the field, it can be deduced that development is actually taking place through the decentralised agencies, the local councils with its partners - FEICOM and PNDP. Figure 1 and 2 presents respondents' views on the impact of decentralisation to the development of basic facilities within the two municipalities of Kumba and Tiko.

Fig. 2: Respondents' view on the impact of decentralisation in Kumba and Tiko
Source: Author (2023)

Figure 2 shows that the health sector is what the inhabitants have had a feel more in both municipalities than for the other sectors. This is especially true with the recent conversion of the Kumba District Hospital to a Regional Hospital Annex and the Preventive Health Centre to a District Hospital respectively. This has not only improved upon the availability of staff and staff strength of the hospitals but has also brought in some specialists to work in these hospitals. This has reduced the dependence of the hospital on other health units out of the town to some extent. The provision of water is the least creating an impact to the population as some of the standpipes created had only function for a few months and now abandoned. Generally, the investment trends from FEICOM and PNDP by sector in the different councils are summarised in Figure 2.

Fig. 3: Trend of investment by sector Study area, Southwest or national?
Source: FEICOM and PNDP Yearly Reports (2020)

From the trend analysis, construction of the Tiko Main market for example in 2013 took the biggest share of the investment funds from FEICOM compared to other areas of investment. This is followed by the recent investments on the pavement of streets and

construction of culverts in Kumba, followed by the construction of main office buildings in Tiko and Kumba I, I and III councils which took another reasonable amount of money. The health and education sectors were given considerable attention; regrettably the energy sector had very little attention while the water sector was completely abandoned as shown in Figure 3. However, this study examines the different areas of development in the Tiko and Kumba Municipalities.

4.2.1 Educational Development

According to Tamukong (2004), the role of education in all aspects of development (economic, social, cultural, technological and scientific) is paramount. For a people to develop, they must acquire sufficient and proper education. He argued that education is a fundamental human right and a key to sustainable development, a key to peace and stability within and among nations and an indispensable means for effective participation in the societies and economies of the twenty-first century.

To this end, both the basic and secondary education sectors have been revamped by the Councils. Classroom construction and the supply of didactic materials to schools to enhance and promote education and improve on the number of children who can obtain basic and secondary education within the municipalities have been successfully carried out by the councils. This activity is in accordance with Decree N° 2010/0247/PM of February 2010 to lay down conditions for the exercise of some powers transferred by the State to local councils relating to basic education. This decree empowers the Council to build, equip, manage and maintain nursery and primary schools as well as pre-school establishments; acquire materials and school supplies; recruit and take charge of support personnel of these schools and establishments. These have been carefully implemented by the councils of Kumba and Tiko Municipalities as illustrated in Plates 1 and 2. Plate 1a illustrates the old Government Primary School structure and Plate 1b shows the newly constructed structure for the school.

Plate 1 a and b: New Government Primary School constructed by PNDP within the Tiko Municipality

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Plate 2: Constructed classrooms at GHS Nkamlikum and GPS Kumba Town Group III
Source: Field Survey (2021)

These buildings have been able to accommodate the extra number of students/pupils who previously could not get admission due to lack of space. It should also be noted that a part of the new building in GPS Kumba Town is currently hosting GHS Kake which has been relocated from Kake due to the current socio-political crisis. This has enabled students and pupils to acquire basic education.

4.2.2 Health Development

Decree N° 2010/0246/PM OF 26 February 2010 to lay down conditions for the exercise of some powers transferred by the state to Councils relating to Public Health states inter alia that “the powers transferred include buildings, maintenance work and management of the integrated Health Centre”. This Law also makes councils part of the management body of government hospitals. Within this framework, a number of health centres have been constructed since 2010 like the Integrated Health Centres of Tiko in 2011, Mudeka in 2011, Missellele in 2013, and Moquo in 2013.

By constructing these health facilities, the population easily has access to healthcare thereby reducing health challenges and distances formally covered by the population to access health facilities. Patients from Mudeka, Missellele and Moquo until now had to travel over 20 kilometres and above to Tiko for consultation. This did not only aggravate their sicknesses due to stress before reaching the Health centre, but the cost of transport played on their finances. Tiko, which is the Chief Town of the Sub-Division had another Health centre added to the existing one in 2011 thereby adding to the already existing number of Health centres. This has tremendously improved on the health conditions of the population. Plate 3 illustrates the new Tiko Health Centre constructed in 2011 adjacent to the old one constructed by the Native Authority of the 1960s; both are being used today to accommodate increasing cases of admission, especially for maternity cases.

(a)

(b)

Plates 3a and b: The old Health Centre (a) and new health centre (b) in Tiko Municipality

Source: Author (2023)

4.2.3 Infrastructural Development

A number of infrastructural developments have been achieved by councils in Kumba and Tiko Municipalities. These developments range from road construction, boreholes, and market construction.

4.2.3.1 Road Construction/Maintenance

This study reveals that with decentralisation in place the road sector has received a boost in this area as there is a steady increase in the investment on road. With this, more quarters and streets have become accessible. Neighbourhoods like Ombe, Misaka, Mondoni native, Mudeka which are typically farming areas in Tiko Sub-Division have become disenclaved. These roads have enabled crops to be brought from farms to markets with relative ease. In Kumba, most of the streets are being paved with bricks to ease the interconnectedness of the neighbourhoods. According to sources from the Kumba City Council, over 18.6km of roads within the Municipality will be paved with bricks by the end of 2025. This will go a long way to ease movement and businesses within the town.

4.2.3.2 Supply of Portable Drinking Water

Water is used daily for many purposes: industry, agriculture and domestic use. According to the World Bank Report (2022), 69% of the 3240 Km³ of fresh water drawn every year are used by farmers, 23% by the industrial sector and 8% for domestic use. In Tiko and Kumba, the main sources of water supply are “La Camerounaise des Eaux”, (CDE), Cameroon Development Corporation (C.D.C) in Tiko especially, Rain water, Mineral water, and the Rivers Kumba and Ndongu. Decree N° 2010/0239/PM of 26 February 2010 laid down conditions for the exercise of some powers transferred by the state to councils relating to safe drinking water supply in areas not covered by the public water distribution network conceded by the state. This decree oblige the Council to provide wells and boreholes to areas not connected to any water network. The Council is

to design and implement sustainable water and sanitation development plans and projects; exploit springs and mineral water and lay down conditions for the protection and exploitation of surface and underground water. In line with this decree, the state has since 2010 allocated the sum of 16 million FRS CFA for the construction of equipped bore holes at G.B.S.S. Mudeka and Mongo Island. To this number, the PNDP added one bore hole at the Mungo Layout Government School as seen in Plate 5 and intended to serve the general public after school hours.

Plate 5: Borehole constructed by PNDP to assists in solving water problems in the Tiko Municipality

Source: Author (2023)

The allocation of bore holes and wells to the Tiko Municipality has fallen short of serving the purpose it is intended. The coastal location of Tiko poses a challenge to the construction of bore holes and wells. All bore holes and wells constructed have been tested and found to have high levels of iron (Fe) that renders the water unfit for drinking but can be used for washing. This has not been able to solve the problem of providing portable drinking water to the people. As a result, about 60% of the Tiko population depends on CDE for water which has become unaffordable for the common man while those in the rural areas depend on wells and the Ndongo River. For this reason many have resort to invade the privacy of the C.D.C. residential area to fetch particularly drinking water which is very scarce. Children spend many hours and cover long distances looking for drinking water. This activity is routine and must be done by them as it is rare to find an elderly person fetching water. This in a way affects the socio - economic life of the people as valuable time is spent to fetch water.

On the other hand, water supply in Kumba has been effective mainly with the use of CDE as mentioned earlier. The council has also constructed some boreholes in areas where public taps are not available like Barombi Mbo, Bonakama and Mpvenye Street. Plate 6 shows a borehole constructed by the council in Bonakama.

Plate 6: Construction of a bore hole at Banakama junction
Source: Field Survey (2021)

The reader can appreciate contributions of local councils to sectoral development and the SDGs but the deprived aspects or lagging indicators are not clearly itemised for a balanced assessment of the role of councils in Regional Development. From the progress made, the study moves straight to the challenges without us not being able to appreciate what is not there in those domains. For instance

Moreover, are the current projects bringing about regional development through the Trickle-Down Effect and through Polarisation?

4.3 Contribution of Kumba and Tiko Councils in Attaining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

In 2015, 195 nations agreed with the United Nation that they can make the world better by bringing together their respective governments, businesses, media, institutions of higher education, and local NGOs to improve the lives of people in their various countries **by 2030**. The Sustainable Development Goals were later adopted and ratified by 193 countries and has emerged as the most inclusive and comprehensive negotiations in the United Nations history. The UN focuses on ideas and initiatives that generate larger impact, advance the SDG imperative to “leave no one behind,” and are backed by evidence, practical commitments, and actions. It is in this light that this work identifies the contribution of the Kumba and Tiko Councils to the attainment of the SDGs.

There are 17 goals within the SDGs. The goals begin with the elimination of poverty, erasing hunger, establishing good health, providing quality education, enforcing gender equality, providing clean water and sanitation, affording clean energy, decent work, industrialization, reduce inequality, creating sustainable cities and communities, enhancing responsible consumption, actions on climate change, protect life below water, life on land, guarantee peace among nations and build partnerships among nations. From the various goals, the state of attainment by Kumba and Tiko Councils are being examined. The councils are noted to have had an impact on Goals 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7. These contributions are explained in the subsequent paragraphs.

Just like any other council in the world, the Kumba and Tiko Councils have the ability and capacity to develop their municipalities irrespective of the numerous challenges faced. National Policies and Priorities are respected in order for the Councils to succeed in reaching the sustainable development goals. This is done by meeting up with their necessary targets following the planning processes and strategies in the domain of

economic, social and environmental fields. Based on this, this study examines each goal with examples of how they have been arrived at by the councils.

GOAL 1: End poverty in all its forms; The Kumba Council has been able in her capacity to reduce poverty by creating job opportunities to the youths of its municipality. This has been achieved through the sponsoring of some 20 (twenty) female youths into vocational training at the Women Empowerment and Family in Kumba in 2019 and 2022. This has helped these youths to create jobs as well as employing others. The Tiko council on its part has been able to recruit youths especially during holidays. Furthermore, the construction of business sites has also enabled the population to get stores at lower cost. This has encouraged development of businesses and a raise in per capital income of their population. All these have been able to provide income to families thereby raising their living standards and putting food on their tables.

GOAL 2: To End Hunger, the population of Kumba and Tiko municipalities are mostly indulged in small scale farming which helps their families for their daily bread. These farmers also market some of the proceeds from their farms for use in family expenses like children's education, health and upkeep. Though most of the farmlands are provided to them by private individuals, the councils work on the maintenance of these farm to market roads to enable farmers carry their crops to the market. Examples in the case of Kumba include the road from Kake I to Barombi Mbo village that was rehabilitated in 2017. Another rehabilitated farm to market road is that from Shobha to Match the same year of 2017. In the case of Tiko Municipality, the Tiko council has opened unclassified rural roads, build crossing infrastructure, take stock of the rural roads concerned, acquire rural road maintenance materials and equipment concerned, clean earth roads, fill potholes, clean and repair bridges, treat swampy areas, fell trees during storms, as well as maintaining and management of rain gates. Tiko Council has 35 kilometres of earth roads within the Municipality to maintain and to create more as the population is growing.

This has encouraged the population of these municipalities to cultivate more food crops. The increase in cocoa prices recently has as well encouraged farmers to produce more and with the construction of the Kumba Mundemba road, transportation of crops have become much easier. Owing to the increase in food production, it is assumed that by 2030, there can be a possible level of sustainable food production that can ensure resilient agricultural practices that will help maintain ecosystems and strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change.

Goal 3: Good health and wellbeing; during the past years, the Kumba and Tiko Councils have been able to contribute in the domain of good health and wellbeing. From 2013, the Councils carried out some projects in the domain of health among which include:

- The construction of a health centre in Big-Ngwandi,
- The construction of a health centre in Bekondo
- Supply of medical equipment to the integrated health centre at Boa-Balondo
- Supply of medical equipment to the Integrated health centre in Big-Ngwandi
- Supply of medical equipment to the Integrated health centre in Bekondo
- In 2014, the construction of an Integrated health centre
- In 2019, the Kumba I Council supplied medical equipment to the Bukweme integrated health centre in the Kumba I municipality.

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

- Construction of Integrated Health Centre in Mudeka
- Construction of Integrated Health Centre in Tiko
- Construction of Integrated Health Centre in Missellele
- Construction of Integrated Health Centre in Moquo

From the above-mentioned medical facilities offered by the Councils, it is clear that they have helped in meeting-up with health provision in their municipalities. These facilities were not provided to be used just for a short term, the councils made sure that it carries out rehabilitation on each building of the different areas after a period of two to three years and medical equipment supplied when need be, thus enhancing the achievement of Goal 3 of the sustainable development goal.

GOAL 4: Ensure quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The Kumba and Tiko Councils have contributed to educational development through the construction of primary and secondary schools in their municipalities. The Kumba council on her part supplied benches to Government Practicing School, Kumba Town Group 1 in 2016. In 2018, she constructed a block of two classrooms at Government Practicing School (GPS) Kumba Town Group III, and in same year, supplied chairs, benches and tables to the same institution. In 2019, the same exercise for benches, chairs and tables were purchased and handed to the Government Practicing School, Kumba Town Group IV. The Tiko council on its part has through its Communal Development Plan of increased the literacy rate by 20% before 2025 through the construction of 65 classrooms for the entire municipality. Most of these were achieved during the first phase that ended in 2015. This has helped improve the learning process and condition of both municipalities. To this light, the study concludes that Goal 4 has been achieved to a larger extent as the institutions have been able to continue training its pupils and students with little difficulty in terms of space and didactic materials needed for efficient training.

Goal 6: To ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; in 2010, the Kumba I Council constructed a modern toilet at GPS Group V in the Kumba I Municipality. This construction was carried out in order to serve the pupils of the Government Practicing School, Kumba Town and improve upon the sanitation condition of the environment as it has put an end to open defecation. In 2015-2016, the Kumba council engaged in the construction of boreholes in Barombi Mbo. A similar exercise took place in 2017 and another construction of a borehole at Mpenye Street, Mile 1, and also in 2018 where two boreholes were constructed at Bonakama. The construction of these boreholes is as a result of the insufficient flow of pipe born water within these communities. The Tiko council on the other hand, has since 2010 allocated over 16 million frs cfa for the construction of equipped bore holes at G.B.S.S. Mudeka and Mongo Island. To this number, the PNDP added one bore hole at the Mungo Layout Government School to reduce distance covered by residents to fetch portable water. These boreholes have been able to serve and solve the water crises of the population thereby meeting up with the challenges of water scarcity and attaining Goal 6 of the SDG.

Goal 7: Sustainable Lighting; the Kumba I Council has been able to provide solar lighting to some communities of its municipality. Solar street lamps have been installed in Bonaka, Krama, Barombi, Ccass street and Up Station. Also, the council was involved in the extension of local public lighting to GHS Kake, a project worth over 10.000.000frs. This has helped enhance the state of lighting especially with the constant epileptic

situation of lighting in Kumba. Though more is expected in this domain owing to the current situation of lighting, the council has been able to make its little contribution in this regard.

From the above analysis, it can be deduced that, the councils of Kumba and Tiko have to an extent been able to contribute to the achievement of some of the SDGs in the South West Region. Lacking in its achievement are Goals 5, 8, 9 to 17, which are caused by a number of challenges.

4.4 Challenges confronting the decentralisation process and achieving the SDG objectives

In achieving the goal of decentralisation, the process has been slowed due to many reasons. The challenges run from conflicting interest in power to lack of finances to properly finance projects. The cry of the local masses in the South West Regions as a whole is the lack of basic commodities to enhance their livelihood such as the lack of basic infrastructure, roads and bridges linking farms to markets, shortage of portable water, electricity, health facilities, recreational and educational facilities.

a. Conflict of Power

Despite enormous task vis-à-vis the municipality, there are institutions that undermine the Councils' efforts to meet these needs and make the accomplishment of its basic task slow. For example, administratively the Governor within the Region and Senior Divisional Officers in the Divisions are the Supervisory Authorities over councils (Art. 41 of Decree N°. 2008/377 of 12 November, 2008). As Mbuagbo and Oroch (2012) put it, this imposition of state-appointedees on locally elected Mayors does not augur well for local democratic practices and is a source of problem plaguing the councils due to conflicting relationships. Decisions taken by the Mayor must be sent to the Supervisory Authority for approval, this puts the elected official under the appointed government authority thereby slowing decision making.

b. Inadequate Finance

Till date, the government treasury still collects most of Council revenue. Most major projects of the Council must go through or be funded by FEICOM. This situation is exacerbated by poor revenue collection strategies, lack of competent human resources to handle the challenges of decentralisation with the devolution of some ministerial functions. Councils lack basic equipment to permit the execution of developmental projects like road construction which have further weakened Councils' ability to satisfy the local population and contribute enormously to achieving the SDGs.

Added to these, the state each year allocates a lump sum of money to be shared among councils in terms of Public Investment Projects, which does not take into cognizance the development pressure of the area for the year. This means the state merely transfer what it is able to get for that year without evaluating the needs on the ground. To this end the state has resorted to selective funding of project which implies they select only projects they think funds for that year can support and go ahead without verifying if that is the immediate need of the people of that area.

c. Diverse interpretations of the Decentralisation texts

The meaning, interpretation and implementation given to the term decentralisation is polysomic and as such it is elusive in obtaining a clear cut type, pattern, model or principles to follow in the process. Findings during this research revealed that uniform meaning and interpretation has not been given to the texts of application by the various actors. Not only are the text difficult to understand by reason of their volume but the perception of the text is also an issue. For example, the phrase “transfer of competencies” (power and resources) has been interpreted by the Mayors to mean a lump sum of money and personnel shall be put at the disposal of the Council for the execution of projects by the Council. But during an interview with the representative of the Pay Master General of the South West Region, he made it clear that the Council manages the money on paper while the State through the treasury disburses the money after a contract has been executed and confirmed by the Council through the issuance of acceptance certificate and a pay voucher. This confusion stems from the fact that the texts talk of transfer of power and resources and goes further to spell out that decentralisation funds is to be made available to Councils whereas it is not the case practically.

At the level of the Ministries, this dilemma of interpretation is evident. According to reports of the last inter-ministerial committees; the issue of competencies was clarified. Ministries were made to understand that the state owned competencies and not the Ministries and so no Ministry should say it has not got enough resources to transfer its competencies (ICLS Report, 2012). It is for this reason that some ministries programmed for the transfer of competencies have complied like the Ministry of Public Works while others are still to.

d. Lack of Synergy between Councils and MINEPAT

Councils have Communal Development Plans which serve as their road maps. It is a data base for all projects and diagnosis of all the sectors for the entire Municipality. This data base has not been communicated to the Ministry of Town Planning and, as such, there is no synergy between projects at the level of the Ministry and those in the CDP. This poses a problem at the level of providing the needs of the population as, most often, MINEPAT data base is obsolete and do not reflect the immediate needs of the people. A typical case in the Tiko Municipality is that of providing portable water to the population. Due to the cost and the distances to carry CAMWATER within the villages in this area, the state resorted to the provision of boreholes. Findings revealed that these boreholes cannot be used for drinking as chemical test reports conducted after construction shows that the water contains high level of iron (Fe). This report was made to MINEPAT; the year after the state allocated borehole to the same area. It was concluded that boreholes are not suitable for the Mongo area due to its proximity to the sea and the high level content of (Fe) in the water. Despite the fact that the boreholes available cannot serve the purpose intended to the population based on its poor quality, the state has still subsequently allocated two more boreholes to the same area. If there existed a synergy between the CDP and MINEPAT, the ministry would have known that boreholes are not needed but rather an extension of CAMWATER to this area to satisfy the needs of the population.

e. Phobia to Transfer Power

It is not easy for one to give up power. Cameroon has had more than 40 years culture of a centralized system so much so that some in power are people who have been managing the system this while. They now find it difficult to see power withdrawn from them and handed to Councils; especially in the areas of projects where they usually execute themselves using either family relations or their cohorts to make sure they make much money for themselves. For example, an interview with Mr. Owono Owono, member of the inter-Ministerial Committee in charge of monitoring the decentralisation process in Yaoundé revealed that the Ministry of Public Works is still to come to terms with transfer of competencies of his ministry because he does not see how the Councils should manage the contract of road side clearing (cantonnement routière). To him this sector involves huge budget and should stay at the level of the ministry for management. The motive of such action this research concluded was greed for personal aggrandizement and lack of acceptance to relinquish the privileges that go with the power they command. 2015 was the deadline set for ministries to devolve their powers but till date, councils are still faced with the realities of lack of devolved powers.

Discussions

Fostering regional growth through a decentralised perspective comes with a number of factors. These factors are geared towards the devolution of powers from the central governments to local councils and the ease with which councils are able to carry out projects to develop their communities. As noted by Oommen (2021), local government's policy and fiscal space allow greater inward investments via community sub-contracting and hiring of local firms for slum upgrading, road construction and other local public works projects. Also it increases the number of employment-intensive infrastructure (as opposed to mechanised) creation and maintenance projects to create jobs, and create socially (schools, hospitals) and economically (marketplaces) supportive infrastructure as realised by current studies. However, such benefits of decentralisation come with a number of challenges. Megele, (2012) points out a host of challenges that local governments face in the 21st Century such as delivery services; lack of finance, trained human resources, engaging citizens, forming new partnership and rapid evolution of technologies, socio-economic developments and changing demographics. The Kumba and Tiko councils are faced with challenges of an appropriate project that can suit the different demographics of their municipalities.

The results equally show that the devolution of powers has empowered local governments to exercise their development visions and initiatives, which steps from local community ideologies. This result is similar to that of (Manyi, 2007) who argue that local councils with have development visions and initiatives, which are promising development initiatives from local community (bottom-up). Naess (2001) further brings to light the fact that it is through empowerment of the local governments that municipal programmed plans and service provisions can have a higher livelihood that reflects local needs more accurately than in centralized systems of governance.

Conclusion

Decentralisation in the last decades has evolved as a modern and widely accepted concept. It was based on the presumption that once power was devolved to the local level of management it would trigger local development and bring the government closer to

the people. This will eventually make development projects sustainable and giving opportunity to the people to hold the actors accountable.

Local governments have a role to bring the government closer to the people and equally used as a medium of implementing decentralisation. These local governments have municipal programmes that plan and ensure service provisions to have a higher livelihood that reflects local needs more accurately. Inherently, local councils lie in creating and maintaining the development of a set of utilitarian values and productive powers of the local arrangement. To examine the council's projects and the extent to which they contribute to sustainable development in the Tiko and Kumba municipalities, the study proves that both councils have been ensuring sustainable development practices through project implementation such as the construction of classrooms, provision of portable drinking water (boreholes) and health care. Despite the positive role identified in the field, challenges faced by the councils in implementing projects for sustainable development, study indicated that they were still lacking in the full potential of power devolution in order for them to realise fully the sustainable development goals through their projects. In view of this, a number of recommendations have been posited to assist local governments meet up with the goal of achieving the SDGs.

Recommendations

Based on the challenges identified and to ensure that the Kumba and Tiko councils achieve the sustainable development goals, the following are recommended:

- ❖ There exist diverse interpretations of the decentralisation texts. To this end, there is need for seminars on interpreting the texts and capacity building in general to all those involved in the implementation of the texts. This must be completed by handing copies of the texts to the stake holders in the language they best understand.
- ❖ The contract to execute local projects should be awarded to a local contractor and by a local Tenders Board. Contracts awarded from Yaounde are difficult to control by local authorities as the contractor tends to be answerable only to authorities in Yaounde. Most often contractors are paid for poorly executed work while the authorities in Yaounde will be aware that the community has been served their request.
- ❖ Councils have their Communal Development Plan elaborated by contributions of a cross section of the stakeholders of that community. This study recommends Mayors to strictly implement projects from the CDP. This document is supposed to serve as the road map for the Councils in providing the needs of the community.
- ❖ There is no synergy between the CDP and the MINEPAT data base for Regional Projects. It is therefore recommended that Councils should send copies of their CDP to the Regional Councils for onward transmission to MINEPAT for updating of its data base and subsequent provision of funds that reflects the needs of the people.
- ❖ Finance could also be gotten through Sponsorship schemes by soliciting for funds from enterprises and nongovernmental organizations interested in community development and sustainability. It is probably the best known and frequently used method of financing local projects today like the World Bank and African Development Bank.

- ❖ Local Councils should also design and market programs and activities geared towards accommodating community members of diverse backgrounds. Programming activities for members of communities that are part of a multicultural, racial or ethnic group will go a long way in promoting sustainable development through inclusion as they could share ideals to ensure local council projects were beneficial to all members of the community.
- ❖ Partnership agreements could help local councils generate the necessary financial aid needed for their projects and also partnership agreements could be seen as an accelerator of development as some partners will decide on projects in the community and execute them.
- ❖ Mobilising the community through enhanced participatory
- ❖ Budgeting and civic participation will engage the citizens and also facilitate enhanced revenue collection. Collection and enforcement must rely on a combination of positive incentives, sanctions and penalties. Positive incentives should be the first approach that is convincing taxpayers and businesses to pay their required taxes and fees by providing improved local services. This will increase resources and also help local councils to implement projects which will lead to a sustainable community development.

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- Law No. 2004/17 of July 2004 on the Orientation of Decentralisation
- Law No. 2004/18 of July 2004 comprising rules applicable to Councils
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